

The Use of the 5W2H Total Quality Management Tool: A Case Study

O Uso da Ferramenta de Gestão da Qualidade Total 5W2H: Um Estudo de Caso
El uso de la herramienta de gestión de calidad total 5W2H: Un estudio de caso

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Ana Laura Madureira da Silva¹
ana.silva2218@fatec.sp.gov.br

Rhadler Herculani¹
rhadler.herculani@fatecbb.edu.br

1 – Fatec Bebedouro – “Jorge Caram Sabbag”

Abstract: *The topic presented addresses the importance of applying total quality management methods to promote a better understanding of the shipping activity in a frozen food company. The objective of this work is to demonstrate the use of the 5W2H method in analyzing discrepancies in the shipping process of a frozen food company in the interior of São Paulo state, in order to identify errors and solve problems. According to theory, the use of tools such as the 5W2H method can significantly contribute to the development of standardization, by allowing detailed monitoring of each stage of the activities. The methodology used was based on bibliographic research, qualitative research, and field research. In addition, the case study identified the problem situation for the application of the chosen quality method. A detailed monitoring of all stages of the operational process was carried out, allowing systematic observation and collection of relevant data. Based on this information, it was possible to identify the critical points where failures occurred. From the analysis, an action plan was developed with corrective and preventive measures, along with efficient operational procedures, to eliminate the problems of discrepancies in shipping loads. In conclusion, this methodology allowed not only the detection of the origin of the failures, but also the implementation of effective improvements, contributing to the reduction of errors and the increase in operational efficiency.*

Keywords: *Disagreements; Processes; Operational Excellence; Improvements; Standard Procedure.*

Resumo: O tema apresentado trata da importância da aplicação de métodos de gestão da qualidade total para promover um melhor entendimento da atividade de expedição em uma empresa de frios. O objetivo desse trabalho é demonstrar a utilização do 5W2H na análise de divergências no processo de expedição de uma empresa de frios no interior paulista a fim de se levantar erros e solucionar problemas. De acordo com a teoria, a utilização de ferramentas como o método 5W2H pode contribuir significativamente para o desenvolvimento da padronização, ao permitir o acompanhamento detalhado de cada etapa das atividades. A metodologia utilizada partiu da pesquisa bibliográfica, pesquisa qualitativa e pesquisa de campo. Além disso, o estudo de caso levantou a situação problema para a aplicação do método da qualidade escolhido. Elaborou-se um acompanhamento detalhado de todas as etapas do processo operacional, permitindo a observação sistemática e a coleta de dados relevantes. Com base nessas informações, foi possível identificar os pontos críticos onde ocorriam as falhas. A partir da análise, desenvolveu-se um plano de ação com medidas corretivas e preventivas, junto com procedimentos operacionais eficientes, para eliminar os problemas de divergências nas cargas da expedição. Conclui-se que essa metodologia permitiu não apenas detectar a origem das falhas,

mas também implementar melhorias eficazes, contribuindo para a redução de erros e o aumento da eficiência operacional.

Palavras-chave: Divergências; Processos; Excelência Operacional; Melhorias; Procedimento Padrão.

Resumen: *El presente trabajo aborda la importancia de aplicar métodos de gestión de calidad total para promover una mejor comprensión de la actividad de envíos en una empresa de alimentos congelados. El objetivo es demostrar el uso del método 5W2H para analizar las discrepancias en el proceso de envíos de una empresa de alimentos congelados en el interior del estado de São Paulo, con el fin de identificar errores y resolver problemas. Según la teoría, el uso de herramientas como el método 5W2H puede contribuir significativamente al desarrollo de la estandarización, al permitir un seguimiento detallado de cada etapa de las actividades. La metodología empleada se basó en investigación bibliográfica, investigación cualitativa e investigación de campo. Además, el estudio de caso identificó la situación problemática para la aplicación del método de calidad seleccionado. Se llevó a cabo un seguimiento detallado de todas las etapas del proceso operativo, lo que permitió la observación sistemática y la recopilación de datos relevantes. Con base en esta información, fue posible identificar los puntos críticos donde se produjeron fallas. A partir del análisis, se desarrolló un plan de acción con medidas correctivas y preventivas, junto con procedimientos operativos eficientes, para eliminar los problemas de discrepancias en las cargas de envío. En conclusión, esta metodología permitió no solo detectar el origen de las fallas, sino también implementar mejoras efectivas, contribuyendo a la reducción de errores y al aumento de la eficiencia operativa.*

Palabras clave: Desacuerdos; Procesos; Excelencia Operacional; Mejoras; Procedimiento Estándar.

1. INTRODUCTION

Many companies seek to improve and standardize their processes through total quality management tools such as 5W2H; however, this goal is sometimes overlooked by employees who are in a hurry and don't care to follow their company's standard operating procedures (SOPs). As a result, a series of errors occurs during the processes, causing problems, hindering effective management practices, and increasing costs due to rework.

By implementing quality standards, offering continuous training, and monitoring indicators, companies reduce these failures and ensure that all employees follow procedures correctly. If any problem reaches customers, they will have a bad impression of the company, since total quality management is directly linked to the reliability of the products and services offered, the efficiency of internal processes, and the ability to innovate and differentiate in the market (Carpinetti, 2010).

According to Carpinetti (2010), applying the 5W2H tool allows us to map the critical stages of processes, understand the causes of failures, propose corrective and preventive actions, and ensure that improvements are implemented, promoting consistency and reliability in all company operations.

The objective of this work is to demonstrate the use of the 5W2H method to analyze discrepancies in the shipping process of a frozen food company in the interior of São Paulo state, thereby identifying errors and solving problems.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 Principles of Total Quality Management

Total Quality Management (TQM) focuses on customer satisfaction, meaning that companies should orient their processes and decisions to meet and anticipate customer needs, as quality is the "continuous correspondence between expectations and deliverables." This principle implies measuring performance across indicators related to satisfaction and perceived value, rather than "not just by technical conformity, which requires systematic data collection and feedback" (AicHouni, Silva, Ferreira, 2024).

Another principle is continuous improvement, which means the involvement and commitment of people at all levels of the company and "depends on empowerment, delegation, and a culture of responsibility, so that workers are active participants in identifying problems and proposing solutions." Recent studies show that, even in the transition to digital environments (Industry 4.0), leadership and employee participation remain crucial for the success of TQM practices. (Canbay ; Akman, 2023).

Another pillar of TQM is the process-based approach and continuous improvement (PDCA cycles, process management, statistical control), which means that "organizing activities as interrelated flows facilitates the identification of variability, waste, and optimization opportunities." Contemporary authors emphasize that data integration and fact-based decision-

making strengthen this pillar, "allowing for faster responses to deviations and promoting operational sustainability" (AicHouni; Silva; Ferreira, 2024).

Other concepts are also important, such as systemic management and an emphasis on results (organizational effectiveness, regulatory compliance, and sustainability), because, in addition to technical compliance, modern companies understand that TQM must align with the company's posture of seeking environmental, social, and economic performance. Sectoral applications, such as in the pharmaceutical and food industries, illustrate the need to align TQM with regulatory requirements and public health protection, demonstrating that quality principles also translate into consumer safety and confidence. (Vassos et al., 2024).

The modernization of TQM (Total Quality Management) gave rise to the term "Quality 4.0," which combines automation tools, big data analysis, and the Internet of Things (Internet of Things). Things - IoT). This special set has enhanced "measurement, traceability, and continuous improvement, but does not replace the human principles of leadership, culture, and participation." In short, contemporary TQM combines customer focus, process management, people involvement, systemic vision, and strategic use of data to promote excellence and sustainability. (Canbay; Akman, 2023; AicHouni; Silva; Ferreira, 2024).

2.2 5W2H Method

In total quality management, many methods are used to create action plans that contribute to development, among them the 5W2H method, which aims to improve and optimize processes.

In accordance with Coletti (2010, p. 5), the 5W2H method is a:

An analytical tool whose objective is to direct discussion to a single focus, avoiding the dispersion of ideas. It is a useful tool in two distinct analytical situations: (a) Verifying the occurrence of a problem, and (b) Developing an Action Plan. This method is also called the 6Ms, in which subjects are grouped by "families": Manpower, Machine, Material, Method, Measurement, and Environment.

The 5W2H tool consists of seven key questions, as shown in Figure 1. The application of the 5W2H methodology involves answering these seven questions. "In practice, no large investments are necessary. To start using the tool, you can use a whiteboard or a spreadsheet" (Maass, 2019).

Figure 1 – 5W2H Tool

Source: Maass, 2019

It is an effective method for companies seeking to improve their management and transform their work processes by helping develop SOPs (Standard Operating Procedures). As stated by Medeiros (2010, p. 12), the 5W2H method "is essential for an organization to standardize tasks; it is a tool that seeks to minimize errors in the work routine and ensures that each employee is able to perform their task independently and with quality."

As claimed by Galbrath (1995, apud Gonçalves 2013, p.45):

Standardization aims not only to eliminate waste and rework, or to minimize the information needed to carry out the activities that make up the process, but primarily to minimize the need for coordination to perform these activities.

For example, the 5W2H method can be applied using Table 1, which presents a strategy for reducing electricity consumption in a factory.

The authors from FIA Business School (2025) report on the applications of 5W2H:

- Project management: detailing objectives, resources, and deadlines to ensure efficient execution.
- Strategic planning: structuring goals and actions to achieve organizational results.
- Problem solving: identifying causes, proposing solutions, and defining clear steps for implementation.
- Product development: planning launches with a focus on the market and available resources.
- Process improvement: mapping activities, identifying bottlenecks, and proposing adjustments.
- Quality management: implementing corrective and preventive actions based on audits or feedback.

Table 1 – Use of the 5W2H method for reducing electricity consumption.

Reducing energy consumption in a factory	
Question	Response
What?	Implement an energy efficiency program.
Why?	Reduce operational costs and contribute to sustainability.
Who?	Maintenance team and production managers.
Where?	In the production areas and offices of the factory.
When?	Starting in the second quarter of 2025, with semi-annual targets.
How?	Install motion sensors, replace lighting with LEDs, and service equipment.
How much?	An estimated budget of R\$ 30,000 for the initial implementation.

Source: Fia Business School, 2025

According to Alves (2021), the 5W2H framework is highly effective for identifying failures and developing strategic action plans.

As maintained by Dos Santos (2020, p.19):

The 5W2H method stands out from other management methodologies for being a simple, complete, and efficient tool. It allows for timely adjustments and modifications, even while action plans are already in place. This is a type of problem-solving method that can be used by anyone with a business or personal focus. Its structure resembles, in some respects, the famous "divide and conquer" approach, as it deeply subdivides planning into several stages, providing an increasingly broad. In other words, it greatly facilitates the systematization and implementation of ideas.

Furthermore, poor process management can bring many problems to the enterprise, such as repetitive or unnecessary activities, wasted time and labor, and frequent errors, and can compromise stakeholder satisfaction and loyalty (Carpinetti, 2010).

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Methodology

This study was based on bibliographic and qualitative research, grounded in the practical analysis of a real operational process within the company where the author works; in other words, it was a field study or case study.

In accordance with Oliveira (2022), bibliographic research involves searching for books, articles, newspapers, and other materials that provide comprehensive information on the study's focus.

Field research, on the other hand, involves investigation grounded in reality, including observations, data collection, analysis, and interpretation of results. The objective is to verify what the subject actually does, rather than what he or she claims to do (Thibes, 2022).

According to Chueke (2012, p.65)

Qualitative research does not seek to enumerate or measure the events studied, nor does it advocate statistical benchmarks in data analysis; the interests are defined as the study develops. Furthermore, from a methodological point of view, it is believed that the best way to capture reality is to allow the researcher to put themselves in the other's shoes.

3.2 Case Study

3.2.1 Company History

This is one of the largest Brazilian companies specializing in intelligence-driven cold chain logistics solutions for the food and agribusiness sectors. It develops logistics solutions ranging from seed distribution for agribusiness to food service restaurants and is committed to delivering positive results for its clients through the superior quality of its services.

With over 25 years in the market, the company operates with varying levels of product complexity, processes, and systems, has operations in all regions of Brazil, and is a benchmark in food safety management (COMFRIO, 2025).

3.2.2 Area of operation

The company offers integrated solutions, from the transport and storage of refrigerated goods to the coordination of in-house operations, always seeking efficiency, continuous improvement and customer satisfaction (COMFRIO, 2025).

3.2.3 Main customers and suppliers

The company has a vast portfolio; however, in terms of studies, it has:

- Key clients: Corteva, Bayer, Syngenta, BRF, Seara, Minerva, Danone and Vigor.
- Main suppliers: Checklist Facil, TOTVS and Docket.

3.2.4 Problem encountered

The company analyzed was facing product discrepancies in deliveries to the end customer, with items frequently missing or arriving in surplus, leading to dissatisfaction and rework.

As a result, the entire shipment would be returned to the company, even when there were extra products, because the invoice did not match the requested quantity. The same applied to shipments of missing products, as the client companies made it clear that the cost of this error would be borne by them.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To resolve this issue, all shipping-related processes were analyzed, with each assigned activity monitored to identify the source of the failure and the cause of the problem.

The 5W2H method was used as an action plan to identify which activity was being lost during the process, resulting in a shortage or surplus of product at delivery to the end customer.

To achieve this, the following steps were carried out:

Table 2 – Using the 5W2H method to solve the problem in the shipping process.

Question	Response
What?	To investigate the reason for product discrepancies in customer deliveries.
Why?	Eliminate product discrepancies in deliveries to the end customer.
Who?	Transportation, PCL and operations sectors
Where?	In the shipping department
When?	At the conference of all loads
How?	Through mapping the entire product shipping and return process.
How much?	No cost.

Source: Prepared by the authors

To discover the source of the discrepancies, the departments implemented detailed monitoring across all stages of the operational process, enabling systematic observation and the collection of relevant data.

Using this mapping, it became clear that the neglected activity was verifying the count during shipping.

During the analysis, it was found that the driver was not performing this count because the vehicle was already sealed. To verify, it would be necessary to

break the seal, which would generate material waste and would not be the best alternative.

Therefore, it was decided that the driver would perform only the weighing, ensuring the weight matched the invoice. In the event of a discrepancy, the vehicle would return to the dock for a new count, performed by the operations checker.

The volumetric analysis process was not performed correctly.

Hence, thanks to the mapping and data collection, the company reorganized the standard operating procedures involved in four stages, which are:

- **Scheduling:** This is the stage in which the transportation department sends a spreadsheet of available vehicles to the client for selection. The client indicates which vehicle was chosen, and the department informs which driver is available to carry out the transport. Loading onto this vehicle will take place during the night shift. After being informed of the load, the driver goes to the client's office, which is attached to the refrigerated goods company (Seara), to pick up the transport document. Immediately afterwards, he goes to the yard to retrieve his vehicle, identified by its license plate, and proceeds to the next process;
- **Volume measurement:** this is the stage at which the driver takes the vehicle to the company's scale for weighing. If the cargo volume differs by more than 0.8% from the weight indicated on the invoice, the weighbridge operator must inform the operational leadership;
- **Delivery to the end customer:** the stage at which the cargo arrives at its destination. The client company unloads the products and checks them against the invoice. If there are discrepancies, the client contacts the sales department, which then notifies Seara's monitoring department that the client did not accept the cargo and that the vehicle will return to the frozen food company. Immediately after this confirmation, Seara contacts the transport company and informs them of the discrepancy. The driver is instructed to complete the remaining deliveries for other clients and then return with the incorrect products;
- **Return:** This is the stage in which the vehicle returns to the company and parks at a designated dock (A or B). Upon parking, the driver goes to the processing plant, hands over the invoice, the processing plant identifies the error in the system, prints an accounting statement (white form) and a liability statement (two colored forms, white and blue), containing a description of the discrepant cargo and the travel costs to be paid by the refrigerated goods company;
- The driver places this document in the vehicle, and the yard attendant, upon positioning the truck at the return dock, takes it to the checker to manually audit the load and fills in the observation column, indicating the quantities of products that differ from the initial order. Regarding the responsibility statement document, after the audit, the driver signs both the white and blue forms. The blue form will remain with the transportation department, and the white form, stapled to the accountability form, will be delivered to the PCL (Planning and Logistics

Control) administration. This generates a driver billing spreadsheet. The PCL disseminates this spreadsheet to the transportation department and leadership. The objective is to ensure awareness and action regarding the discrepancies. Finally, the transportation department files the accountability report, ensuring process control and traceability.

5. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The application of the 5W2H method enabled detailed mapping of all stages of the product shipping and return process, identifying flaws that caused excesses or shortages in deliveries and affected customer satisfaction. Based on this analysis, corrective and preventive measures were implemented, including checklists, SOPs, and training, to ensure standardization and the correct execution of activities.

With this tool, it was possible to organize activities for error detection in the company's shipping process and to develop new process standards to eliminate these errors.

The results showed that internal audits and continuous improvement actions are essential for reducing errors, rework, and waste and increasing the reliability of products and services for customers.

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